

RESEARCH PAPER

COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS ANALYSIS OF ADIABATIC FLUID FLOW IN GRADUALLY CONTRACTING TRANSITION DUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) was used to simulate fluid flow in ducts of varying diameters. Three Transition ducts of equal inlet areas but different outlet diameters were designed and analyzed. Fluid (water) with inlet velocity of $0.12m/s$ and temperature of $15^{\circ}C$ ($288.15K$) was passed adiabatically through the first transition duct of inlet diameter $11.28mm$ and outlet diameter of $3.57mm$. The analyses of the flow reveals a change of approximately $0.1K$ (-273.05) in temperature in the first duct while the other two ducts also have the same amount of temperature change because of the adiabatic condition of the flow (there was no heat gain or loss by the fluid). Head loss due to pressure variation was recorded as the outlet area changes. The duct with outlet diameter of $3.57mm$ has minimum pressure of $-67.60Pa$ and maximum pressure of $781.70mm$ while the second duct with outlet diameter of $6.67mm$ has $-81.22Pa$ and $245.30Pa$ as its minimum and maximum pressure respectively. The last duct with outlet diameter of $8.67mm$ has $-163.70Pa$ and $319.80Pa$ as its minimum and maximum pressure respectively.

KEYWORDS: Pressure, Temperature, Heat Transfer, Inlet diameter, Force, Fluid Equation

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INTRODUCTION

Pipes are the essential media through which fluids (liquid or gases) are conveyed from one point to another under the influence of a gravity force or a pump to provide the needed pressure (Alexopoulos *et al.*, 2002). When a fluid flows, it encounters friction between layers of the fluid and the pipe walls, and internal friction between the layers of the liquid; giving rise to change in energy (energy losses, in terms of fluid height) known as head losses (Hu *et al.*, 2005, Skye *et al.*, 2006).

One of the common problems encountered in fluid mechanics is the computation of pressure (head) losses. Estimating pressure losses is essential because having the knowledge of the magnitude of frictional losses paves way for the determination of the power requirements of pump to be used to force fluid through pipe. These losses are grouped into major losses present throughout the length of the pipe or minor losses occurring due to minor appendage and accessories present in a pipe network. The appendage encountered by the fluid flow is either sudden or gradual changes of boundaries, resulting from change in magnitude, direction or distribution of flow of velocity (Muralami *et al.*, 2002).

In sudden enlargement, the area of the pipe increases suddenly along the length of the pipe so that the downstream velocity lowers more than the upstream velocity. According to Satish *et al.* (2013), the energy lost is because of the turbulence which depends on the difference in pipe diameters. On the other hand, an increase in pressure loss is caused because of flow separation in the vicinity of sudden contraction plane; this affects erosion rates, heat and

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mass transfer rates at separation and reattachment points. In this work, three transition ducts of equal inlet diameters but different outlet diameters are subjected to fluid flow with different degree of pressure, inlet temperatures and velocities to ascertain the degree of pressure effect on the ducts and magnitude of change in temperature in the ducts.

METHODOLOGY

The input and output parameters used for the analysis of the three ducts are presented in Table 1. The angle (α) shows gradual contraction in size of the ducts while the input temperatures (T) and Velocities (u_i) are the initial conditions of the fluid at the entrance region. The input diameter (d_1) is constant for the three ducts while the output diameter (d_2), varies for all. The transition ducts were drawn in Solidworks Software according to the dimensions given in Table 1. These were then imported into ANSYS environment in which meshing was done and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) was also carried out to analyze the flow of the fluid in the different ducts. The meshing option is as shown in Figure 1.

Using CFX from the ANSYS Software toolbar, the material was set to water, normal speed at 12m/s and static temperature at 15°C for the first duct as shown in Table 1. Also, the whole process was set to Adiabatic, indicating that there was no heat transfer to or from the wall. After running the solution for the first duct, the speed and static temperature are then changed for the second and third ducts as provided in Table 1. The time rate of change of momentum of the fluid particle equals the force acting on it (Newton's Second Law).

$$F = \text{mass} \times \text{acceleration} \quad (1)$$

Since the flow is steady, non-viscous and incompressible, then the forces on a cylindrical fluid element are:

- Pressure force acting on the direction of flow (PdA)
- Pressure force acting on the opposite direction of flow ($(P+dP)dA$)
- A component of gravitational force acting on the opposite direction of flow ($dW\sin\theta$).

Hence, the total force acting on the flow is the sum of gravitational force and forces due to pressure.

Pressure force in the direction of flow:

$$F_p = PdA - (P + dP)dA = -dPdA \quad (2)$$

Gravitational Force in the direction of flow:

$$F_g = -dW\sin\theta; \quad W = mg = \rho dAdLg$$

$$\sin\theta = \frac{dz}{dL}; \quad \therefore F_g = -\rho g dAdz \quad (3)$$

Net Force in the direction of flow

$$F = ma; \text{ but } m = \rho dAdL; \text{ Therefore, } F = \rho dAdLa$$

$$\text{Hence, } F = \rho dAudu \quad (4)$$

Incorporating equations 2, 3 and 4;

$$\rho dAudu = -dPdA - \rho g dAdz$$

Now eliminating ρdA

$$\frac{dP}{\rho} + udu + gdz = 0 \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) is called Euler's equation of motion.

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Integrating equation (5);

$$\frac{p}{\rho} + \frac{u^2}{2} + zg = \text{Constant}$$

$$\therefore \frac{\Delta P}{\rho} + \frac{u^2}{2} + g\Delta z = 0 \quad (\text{Bernoulli's Equation}) \quad (6)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ANALYSIS OF SOFTWARE SIMULATION

It has been stated that the analysis is set to adiabatic, which means that there was no transfer of heat to or from the wall of the duct. However, during the flow, there was a slight increase in temperature of the fluid (Skye *et al.* 2006). The temperature change which is visible in the temperature plot is as shown in Fig. 2 and is negligible because throughout the analysis, heat transfer option was set to Adiabatic Process. Hence, the difference between minimum and maximum temperature along the pipe is very small (0.001K). This slight change of temperature might be because of the bombardment of within water molecules and on the wall of the duct. This undulated flow of the water along the pipe causes increase in momentum of the water molecules. A negligible heat transfer occurs in the entrance and constricted region and becomes uniform as the flow continues (Fig. 3). This is so because of the initial temperature of the fluid and adiabatic process that was set in the beginning of the analysis. However, the slight increase is because of the momentum that changes as the velocity and temperature increase. This increase causes the bombardment of the molecules against one another and the wall which result to a slight temperature change which in turn causes the negligible heat transfer on the walls of the ducts. The heat transfer is affected by an increase in outlet diameter as shown in Figures 5 and 7. When a fluid flows in pipes, there is a considerable rise in pressure on the walls of the pipes and a drop in the pressure of flow that occurs as a result of resistance to flow. Liquid in tension has negative absolute pressure. There may also be a pressure gain/loss due to a change in elevation between the start and end of the duct.

From the pressure plot for the flow (Figures 8, 9 and 10), it is visible that overall length of impact made by the maximum pressure on the wall reduces as the outlet diameter increases. Its concentration is maximum at the point where the area of the duct begins to change (Fig. 8). This is a critical region that needs optimum design to withstand unexpected rise in pressure that may result in pipe damage. This overall pressure difference across the pipe is related to a number of factors which are:

- Friction between the fluid and the wall of the duct
- Friction between adjacent layers of the fluid itself
- Friction loss as the fluid passes through any duct fittings, bends, valves, or components
- Pressure loss due to a change in elevation of the fluid.

These factors decide the pressure gain/loss in different areas of the duct as seen in the three pressure plots mentioned above.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, three different transition ducts with equal inlet areas but different outlet areas have been analyzed using CFD in ANSYS software package to study the effect of fluid pressure on changing outlet areas. As the input velocity increases, pressure increases towards constricted area of the ducts. Also, the analysis of adiabatic has been done and results show that during this process there is no heat gain or loss to or from the wall of the duct.

From the temperature plot, it is essential to always expect a slight temperature increase in fluid flow even in adiabatic conditions as the bombardment of fluid molecules with one another and the wall of the transition duct can give rise to increase in temperature. Hence engineers have to put this in mind in order to have unaltered conveying of fluid from one point to another both in summer and winter period.

Angle of inclination or declination of the ducts is another essential aspect of this analysis. It is obvious that as the fluid comes from a larger area to smaller area, its flow might change from one type to another. As could be seen from the pressure plot, sharp edges should be avoided as these are susceptible to damage due to pressure. Fillet should

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rather be used because the third transition duct has its pressure concentrated around the contraction area. This is essential for the chemical, design and production engineers and other related fields as the material type needed for turbulent flow might be different from that of Laminar flow. Failure to utilizing the appropriate material for the right flow might result in bursting of the pipe which in turn can lead to death, damage of properties, loss of aquatic and terrestrial lives, etc.

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Table 1: Input parameters of ducts and fluid

Duct	u_1 (cm/s)	α^0	T($^{\circ}$ C)	d_1 (mm)	d_2 (mm)
1	1	2	20	11.28	3.57
2	2	4	45	2.5	11.28
3	4	8	60	4.0	11.28

Fig. 1: Meshing options for the three transition ducts

Fig. 2: Temperature plot for the duct of 3.57mm of 3.67mm outlet diameter

Fig. 3: Heat transfer plot for duct of 3.57mm outlet diameter

Fig. 4: Temperature plot for the duct of 6.67mm outlet diameter

Fig. 5: Heat transfer plot for duct of 6.67mm outlet diameter

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Fig. 6: Temperature plot for the duct of 8.67mm outlet diameter

Fig. 7: Heat transfer plot for duct of 8.67mm outlet diameter

Fig. 8: Pressure plot for duct of 3.57mm outlet diameter

Fig. 9: Pressure Plot for Duct of 6.67mm outlet diameter

Fig. 10: Pressure Plot for Duct of 8.67mm outlet diameter